

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

D1.1 – Internal rules and procedures to the consortium

Executive Summary

The internal rules and procedures applicable to the PALOMERA EU funded project are primarily defined in the Consortium Agreement signed between all the beneficiaries, funded and unfunded. In addition to which a Project Information Management System (PIMS) implemented in Confluence¹ provides a full knowledge base regarding the organisational management of the PALOMERA Project. The Project Information Management System (PIMS) is based on the FitSM Standard². This deliverable describes these rules and procedures. It explains the overall functioning within the consortium and the rules that must be respected by each partner, on the one hand to be in line with obligations written in the Grant Agreement, and on the other hand to ensure fluid, efficient and respectful interactions between partners. It is intended to provide guidance and direction for internal governance and management, escalation procedure, internal communication, reporting procedures and internal review process applicable to the project outputs.

Keywords

Consortium management. Project Information Management System. Internal rules, monitoring.

Disclaimer:

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¹ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

² <https://www.fitsm.eu/> for IT service management

Document identification

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Project manager (Quality)	Céline Bitoune (OPERAS)	2023/04/27

³ Use 2.0, 2.1, etc. if the version is updated after the EC rejection.

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	
ALLEA	European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
AMU	Université D'Aix Marseille
CC 0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DACH	Deutschland (Germany), Austria, Confœderatio Helvetica (Switzerland)
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
ED&I	Equity, Diversity & Inclusivity
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
ExCom	Executive Committee
FAIR	Findable. Accessible. Interoperable. Reusable.
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
M#	Project Month <number>
MWS	Max Weber Stiftung
NB	Nota bene
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Book Network

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OABT	OAPEN OA Books Toolkit
OAeBU	Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OATP	Open Access Tracking Project
OBP	Open Book Publishers
OER	Open Educational Resource
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OS	Open Science
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (while in this document it will be referred to as Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan)
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors
PIMS	Project Information Management System
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RPO	Research Performing Organizations
SPARC Europe	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UGOE	Georg August Universität Göttingen
UC	University of Coimbra
UNIBI	University of Bielefeld
WP#	Work Package <number>
ZRC SAZU	The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

2 Introduction

The Consortium Agreement contains provisions about the project governance and management describing in detail the decision-making processes, the liabilities of the beneficiaries, and the handling of intellectual property rights within the consortium. The Project Information Management System (PIMS) complements these regulations with a set of documentation to support the management processes and procedures, templates, and monitoring the use of the resources. Both the Consortium Agreement and the PIMS were developed during the first three months of the project. This is why the submission of this deliverable has fallen behind for one month. The effort and resources have primarily supported the implementation of the internal procedures and the writing and discussion of the consortium agreement. It is these procedures and regulations that are presented in this deliverable.

3 Project consortium rules & bodies

The following PALOMERA partners will take part in the application of the rules and procedures described in the report to sustain effective and smooth project coordination:

OPERAS			
OAPEN	 YOUR PARTNER IN SCIENCE		
HANKEN	ZRC SAZU		
IBL-PAN	 Socialement engagée		
UGOE			
LIBER			
COIMBRA			
Sparc Europe			

Table 1 PALOMERA partners

3.1 Contractual obligations

The beneficiaries are bound by two legal contracts:

- the Grant Agreement regulated by Horizon Europe programme and its financial guidelines; Palomera's GA has been signed on 24 October 2022.
- the Consortium Agreement based on the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe⁴; Palomera's CA signed on March 24, 2023.

Altogether they define the legal obligation of the beneficiaries, the rules of participation, internal and external, the description of the activities, resource and budget allocated to the project.

3.2 Governance and Management chart

The consortium bodies are described in the consortium agreement adopted by all the beneficiaries. It is based around the daily operations of the consortium as developed in the description of action, and on the evolution of the consortium in terms of financial aspects and changes of the description of action. **Figure 1** presents PALOMERA management structure as it has been agreed, ensuring effective project control without unnecessary overhead, based on well-defined procedures and roles.

Figure 1 Project management and governance chart

Acronyms used in the chart: WP: work packages; PCT: Project coordination team; KO: Kick-off

⁴ version 1, December 2022. See: <https://www.desca-agreement.eu/desca-model-consortium-agreement/>

Figure 2 shows the synergy of the organisation in five work packages (WPs) with the WP1 ensuring the administrative coordination for the consortium and the scientific coordination of the three central WPs (WP2, WP3, and WP4). The WP5 takes care of communication and dissemination activities, ensuring the co-creation and validation process of WP2, WP3, and WP4.

Figure 2 PERT chart

3.3 Decision making and conflict resolution

3.3.1 Decision making

The General Assembly is responsible for ensuring the strategic decisions of the project and ratifying all changes to the Description of Action, budget and resources allocated to achieve the project goals, article 6.2 and following of the CA. It is the project's central decision-making body (Art 6.3.1 of the CA) and encompasses one representative per partner and is chaired by the project coordinator. A meeting of the General Assembly is planned for each reporting period (e.g., M8 and M23) to validate the periodic report prior to its submission (CA 6.2.2.1).

The Executive committee is responsible for the day-to-day activities of the project. It is composed of the WP leaders and the project coordination team (OPERAS and OAPEN). It oversees the operational coordination of the activities of the Project. It will monitor risks related to the project implementation and propose mitigation measures and corrective actions. This is described in section 6.3.2 of the Consortium Agreement.

Bi-monthly meetings including all work package leaders ensure a close monitoring of the ongoing activities to identify potential delay or deviations and make appropriate decisions to support the implementation of the plan of action in its original text (GA).

3.3.2 Conflict resolution

From the CA: *“In case the terms of this Consortium Agreement conflict with the terms of the Grant Agreement, the terms of the latter shall prevail. In case of conflicts between the attachments and the core text of this Consortium Agreement, the latter shall prevail.”*

Effective conflict resolution begins with an understanding of the individual and collective management roles. As a rule, the project management represented by the Project Coordination Team (PCT) will aim towards a goal of consensus building, promoting mediation over voting to ensure a maximum degree of cooperation within the consortium. When a conflict arises between members of the consortium, the following escalation process will be followed:

1. WP level

- 1.1. One of the disputing parties sends an email explaining the situation to the relevant work package leader with the disputing party in copy, allowing the other party to reply if so desired. If one of the WP leaders is among the disputing parties, step 2 is engaged.
- 1.2. Action and outcome
 - + the WP leader can successfully resolve the conflict,
 - if no resolution is achieved, go to step 2.

2. Executive Committee level

- 2.1. The WP leader raises the issue with the ExCom via a zoom meeting.
- 2.2. Action and outcome
 - + If the conflict does not have a direct legal or financial impact on one of the members of the consortium, the ExCom builds consensus or opts for an absolute majority vote if no consensus is achieved.
 - if the conflict has a direct legal or financial impact on one of the members of the consortium, the ExCom must formulate an action plan for resolution to be presented to the General Assembly and proceed to step 3.

3. General Assembly level

- 3.1. The project coordination team (PCT) communicates the situation to the General Assembly with an email summarising: the conflict; partners involved/impacted; actions already taken; and the action plan proposed by project management and proposes a decision without a meeting as per consortium agreement article 6.2.2.5.
- 3.2. Action and outcome:
 - + The disputing parties accept the proposal for resolution,
 - The General Assembly votes to accept the proposed resolution which must be accepted by the disputing parties, following the terms of article 6.2.3.4 of the consortium agreement, by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast (anonymous vote and excluding the partners directly involved/impacted).

In addition, veto rules have been defined to guarantee the right of all beneficiaries to be able to challenge a decision taken by a body. They are described in the section 6.2 of the Consortium Agreement (version 0.1, 2023-03-24) and listed here after:

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- Each Consortium Body⁵ shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum).
- If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Body shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.
- Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.
- A Party which the General Assembly has declared according to Section 4.2 to be a Defaulting Party may not vote.
- Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.

4 Internal communication

4.1 Meetings and video conferencing

Most of the meetings will be held online. To that end, a Zoom room is dedicated for project usage. It is currently used for the bimonthly work package leader meetings and for work packages' dedicated meetings. A shared google calendar meetings@operas-eu.org, is used to check the zoom room availability and to avoid double booking.

In addition, a Mattermost⁶ workspace has been created on OPERAS server. It provides a secured space to facilitate collaboration and communication within the consortium and among the partners. Besides it hosts three other major projects, focused on Diamond publishing and addressing complementing objectives, DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA and OAeBU Data Trust, offering them a relatively privileged space, accessible with the same identification (OPERAS ID), to support cross projects collaboration.

As best practice the mailing lists shall be used for important messages and Mattermost is privileged for quick 1:1 discussion or within a limited group of persons.

4.2 Mailing lists and chat

11 targeted mailing lists have been created to ensure fluid communications within the consortium of partners. Each list is managed by the owner and one deputy. The mailing lists service is powered by SYMPA⁷ and provided by Open Edition

⁵ Consortium Body means any management body as described in Section 6 (Governance Structure) of the Consortium Agreement.

⁶ Open-source, self-hostable online chat service with file sharing, designed as an internal chat for organisations and companies.

⁷ <https://www.sympa.org/>, OpenEdition server providing access to a mailing list environment.
Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International

Project mailing lists

- palomera-pct@operas-eu.org [Project consortium team]
- palomera-wpl@groups.openedition.org [WP leaders' group]
- palomera-wp1@groups.openedition.org [WP1 group]
- palomera-wp2@groups.openedition.org [WP2 group]
- palomera-wp3@groups.openedition.org [WP3 group]
- palomera-wp4@groups.openedition.org [WP4 group]
- palomera-wp5@groups.openedition.org [WP5 group]
- palomera-ab@groups.openedition.org [advisory board]
- palomera-pca@groups.openedition.org [project consortium assembly]
- palomera-fal@groups.openedition.org [finance administration and legal]
- palomera-all@groups.openedition.org [members altogether]

The subscription to the mailing lists has been done by the coordination team at the beginning of the project and will continue, upon request, during the whole project duration. The Project manager is in charge of updating the mailing lists to ensure a proper level of information of the different human resources contributing to the project. Each member of the mailing list is allowed to send a message and to send a reply to all.

In parallel to the classic mailing lists, devoted to formal and official information, the consortium uses a messenger tool for daily operational topics. The Mattermost open-source tool allows to create channels (public or private) and to invite only the people concerned by the task to join the channel. On the other hand, the tracking thread allows each colleague to quickly find links to documents. The coordination team uses the OPERAS Mattermost account and OPERAS-ID to register and then access different tools and services from the OPERAS-ID single sign on system.

4.3 Document repository

OPERAS has moved from Google Drive to Google Shared Drive to set controls and confidentiality over files owned or made available by OPERAS AISBL at the level of the organisation, or a team within the organisation, rather than an individual. This fits very well with the purpose of a collaborative project such as PALOMERA. Every file produced and saved on its repository throughout the project duration, even if team members leave, will remain available thus avoiding potential data loss. Like Google Drive it facilitates accessibility, co-writing and co-producing data; team members can keep sharing information and work anywhere, from any device. Folders dedicated to research participants have restricted access with passwords for Work Package Leaders involved in data collection and analysis.

4.4 Collaborative space

The Project Information Management System is implemented in Confluence, a web-based wiki, an online platform where the project partners can structure, organise, and work on shared documents in the cloud. Each team can create dynamic pages to collaborate on project activities. Through shared work every team member has visibility on the progress of the work. The PALOMERA IMS provides a full knowledge base on the project activities and management.

Figure 3 Confluence PALOMERA PIMS

5 Resource monitoring tool

5.1 EUfin

EUfin⁸ provides an online web-based platform to monitor efforts consumption and project costs. The use of the resource is collected at the level of the work package and per beneficiary, both in terms of efforts and costs. The comparative analysis with the project plan is facilitated

⁸ <https://eufin-projectmanagement.eu/>

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through dynamic pivot tables. One to two persons from each partner and affiliated will be granted access to the tool. The list of people pre-defined includes all members of the financial mailing list. Other entities involved in the process include the Project manager, who provides support to the reporting process, the Scientific Coordinator who oversees that the status of the work is consistent with the efforts consumed, and the work package leaders who ensure that the activity and deviations are accurately justified and reported.

5.2 Reporting Calendar

IP stands for Intermediate Period and PR stands for Periodic Report.

	2023		2024	
Jan	M1		M13	
Feb	M2		M14	
Mar	M3		M15	
Apr	M4		M16	
May	M5		M17	
Jun	M6	IP 1.1	M18	IP 1.2
Jul	M7		M19	
Aug	M8		M20	
Sep	M9	1st PR	M21	
Oct	M10		M22	
Nov	M11		M23	
Dec	M12		M24	2nd PR

5.3 Reports timeline

Intermediate reports will be implemented to monitor the efforts used, review and take corrective actions as necessary in case of over or under consumption. Two intermediate reports are planned. Due to the project reporting period, both are planned during summer. Nevertheless, beneficiaries will be informed in advance and made aware of the relevance of this exercise, for the consortium and for them to identify deviation as earlier as possible. The plan is as follows:

Intermediate reports:

- M1-M6: estimate efforts and personnel costs used due at M6+20 days; 20 July 2023
- M10-M18: estimate efforts and personnel costs used due at M18+20 days; 20 July 2024

Periodic reports:

- M1-M09: 1st Financial reporting:
 - **actual effort** due at M09+20 days; 21 Sept 2023
 - **actual costs** used due at M09+30 days; 31 Oct 2023
 - **submission date deadline** to EC: 30 Nov 2023

- M10-M24: 2nd Financial reporting:
 - **actual effort** due at M24+20 days; 21 Jan 2025
 - **actual costs** used due at M24+30 days; 31 Jan 2025
 - **submission date deadline** to EC: 28 Feb 2025

6 Deliverable process

A total of 12 deliverables and 11 milestones will provide regular continuous assessment of the project performance and achievements. These reports and paramount milestones go through a formal review process set up in the procedure “PM01 Deliverable and milestones review”. The whole process shall be completed within 6 to 8 weeks. In case of delay, the author leader will inform the project coordination team and take the necessary actions to minimise the impact of the lateness.

6.1 Review process

The review process is a procedure of the project management referenced under “*PM01 Deliverable and milestones review*”. It sets the individual involved in the procedure, the stages and timeline. It consists in three phases: the deliverable preparation, including the review, the quality control, and the EC approval. In addition to the procedure, best practices and checklists are made available to guide the deliverable leader and reviewer(s) in their tasks. The review is performed to ensure that the output is compliant with the objectives of the project and the formal requirements established in the Grant Agreement. It is based on several following criteria:

- consistency of the overall document,
- relevance of the material,
- format of the document according to Palomera template,
- language and misspelling.

The work package leader, unless s/he is the lead author herself, approves the final version of the deliverable and/or milestone.

6.2 Entities involved in the procedure

Everyone working in Palomera can review the deliverables, depending on their expertise on the various topics.

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The review of deliverables involves minimum two reviewers, appointed by the work package leader who agrees a priori their review role and informing the project manager by email. The review of milestones is performed by the project manager and one member of the scientific coordinator. These roles are defined hereafter:

Lead author: The person from the activity and the partner who is responsible for the document and for collecting input from relevant project tasks. They may rely on others within the activity to provide and/or collect the information needed. The Lead author and co-authors cannot be reviewers.

Project Manager / Quality Manager (PM/QM): Responsible for the review of milestones and deliverables. Check if the deliverable/milestone covered all needed topics and the status of work presented in the document is according to the plan. Provides administrative support for the process.

Scientific Coordinator (SCO): Responsible for the review of milestones and deliverables. Check if the deliverable/milestone covered all needed topics and the status of work presented in the document is according to the plan.

Work Package leader (WP leader): Responsible for overseeing the production of the document. The Work Package leader will work with the Lead author and co-authors to ensure that the work is done in a timely manner, and report to the PM on its progress.

Reviewers: they must not contribute to the deliverable to perform an independent, non-biased assessment.

Internal reviewer: appointed from within the WP.

External reviewer: appointed from outside the WP, from within the consortium or from external Board, such as Advisory Board in Palomera.

6.3 Quality control

The final review prior to submission is planned one week before the submission and is completed by the quality manager. In Palomera this role is delegated to the project manager also WP1 leader. A deliverable checklist (cf. Appendix 1) is established to guarantee a systematic review process.

Appendix 1 - deliverable checklist

Created by [Celine Bitoune](#)

Last updated: [Mar 01, 2023](#)

Content

- Does the deliverable include an acronym table? a definition table?
- Does the document contain an “Executive summary” and can it be read separately?
- Does the document contain an “Introduction” and is it well structured with a plan?
 - Avoid being too generic, or copy-paste from the DoA impact section.
- Is the scope and content of the deliverable in line with the deliverable description in the DoA?
 - If it isn't, is this properly justified, and what is the (new) plan?
- Are the objectives of the deliverable clearly stated?
 - and is the content consistent with its objectives?
- Is the scientific/technical approach sound and adequate?
- Is the quantity of data/information presented adequately?
- Does the content justify the length?
- Are the figures and tables all necessary and correctly referenced?
- Are the figures and tables complete (e.g. content, numbers and captions), clearly presented and of good quality?
- Do statistics and metrics refer to the target or any other information to understand the figures provided?
 - Eg measures expressed following the BTS model (base-target-stretch) with 3 figures respectively for the minimal, realistic and optimist scenarios, except for those where the number is 1, of course.
- Are key performance indicators (KPIs) identified? And are they relevant for the project and identifiable for the project?
 - Eg if unique users/followers/visitors is mentioned, make sure that it is possible to identify them specifically for the project
 - KPIs aren't simple metrics but a combination of several metrics that tell you how you are progressing towards your goal(s). For example audience is the metric that one will use to measure dissemination within several stakeholder groups, and to assess impact (KPI) according to the type of audience. This information will serve to adapt your dissemination strategy.
- Are the references cited relevant and up to date?
 - Does the document history mention all the contributors?
 - Are all the cited references linked with the source in the footer or as hyperlinks?
 - Do hyperlinks and references work?

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- Is the deliverable written in British English, with good syntax and grammar, and adequate language for the target group(s)? Are grammar and spelling checks ok?
- Does the document include a conclusion?

Quality control & format

- The correct template is used
- The title, numbers, type and dissemination level are aligned with the DoA?
- The Format is consistent (numbering, font type, font size, colours, tables and graphs, images)?
- The deliverable includes an acronym table (symbols or abbreviations used in the deliverable are listed or referenced in the footer?)
- The document identification is completed and aligned with the DoA and key words are provided
- The document history and quality control are properly filled in
- The Dissemination level is accurate
- The table of contents is up-to-date (it's an easy-to-forget one!)
- Links are clickable and in the page footers
- Images, Graph, tables are clear and readable
- Grammar and typos are checked
- The document is saved under the correct filename "Palomera_DX.X vX_status"

The deliverable is saved:

- in the shared drive
- posted in Confluence
- and Zenodo or other open platforms as appropriate
- the upload into the EC portal is successful

